

NANOTECHNOLOGY IN FUTURE EDUCATION

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Abstract

Tomorrow's future is strictly based on today's students. Students are considered as a preliminary basic building block for the construction of huge society. Thus, the student's must be expected to develop good moral skills not only for their basic necessities or requirements but to groom themselves as an essential part of country's economic growth and technological advancements. The task of teacher here plays an important role no matter whether s/he is a mentor, guider, philosopher, educator or an expert, whose responsibility is not just to inculcate appropriate skills in the minds of students but inside and outside the classroom activities also. The expected future scenario is quite different from the present traditional classroom situation. The classroom does not mean confined only to the four walls of a room, but it should inculcate the use of latest tools, devices and gadgets in modern classroom teaching practices. The paradigm shift has been taken place for the transmission of learning to reshape the classroom for global perspectives in order to fulfill the visions of 2020. The paper has the objective to find out the opinion of students towards utilizing future gadgets that can be used for educational purposes. The findings show that a vast majority of students have positively opined towards utilizing the future gadgets in classroom practices. This study conclusion that students are interested for global competition to find their own standpoint in the world.

KEYWORDS : Nanotechnology, Nano Informatics, Nano Worlds, Future Technology, Educational Technology, Futurology.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nanotechnology is a new emerging field of today's research and development that finds its applications in a wide range of spectrum. A nano is one billionth of a meter or 10^{-9} m. Its most important applications are in nanotubes, nanoparticle, nanomedicines, nanobiotechnology, green nanotechnology and nanorobotics etc., where as the umbrella term

for nanotechnology is nanomedicines. Nanotechnology is being used more rapidly and progressively in the developed countries such as USA, UK, Canada etc. But in the developing countries like India, it is being used in biological fields to cure diseases towards health issues. The other broader areas of its applications are in the industrialization and environmental concerning issue. In environmental sciences, such as purification of water, recycling and reuse of water system, water filtration, filtration of ground water and other nanoremediation, it has its vast applications. But in industrialization, nanotechnology used in constructing many materials, nanoparticles, arms and ammunition, nano-machines consisting of nano tubes, nanoroda, nanodevices etc. In medical sciences, nanopattering with quantum dots are being used in the manufacturing process of nanomedicines. Thus evolutionary nanotechnologies not only affect the companies and industries but also on large extent to education and IT sectors also.

Basically nanotechnology often divided into two parts one is itself nanotechnology and other is nanoscience are two different words – Nanotechnology involves the manufacturing, designing, execution and implementation of instruments, materials and equipments with unique sixe properties, these nanoparticles so called made up of nanostructures behaves differently in different atomic and molecular forces. Researchers using these nano properties of structures to create something new and exciting tools, devices and products for the advancement in the science, technology and various other fields. The second ‘nanoscience’ is a term where researchers are used to learn about the chemical and physical properties of the materials, products and nano structures. The nanostructures have 1-100 nanometer (nm). Thus, any smallest or tiny materials, things or objects can be made from it. The nanofabrication involves two approaches top-down nano fabrication and bottom up nano fabrication. The top-down fabrication process involves the manufacturing of nano materials from the long materials whereas the bottom up process of nano fabrication incorporated nanostructures from individual atoms or molecules i.e from atom/molecules to be build upward to make nanostructures.

Nano World: Nano Technology

The emergence of the term ‘nanotechnology’, is from instrumentation field. According to Alaxander Huw Arnall, from his book “Future Technologies, Today’s Choices”,

“Nanotechnology means that manipulations, observation and measurement at a scale of less than 100 nanometres (one nanometer is one millionth of a millimetre). In most of the literatures nanotechnology is considered under headline “Nanotech is Godzilla”, that is the “dark side of nanotech: hazardous substances, military applications and a huge leap in corporate power”. Thus, the technology can have both the constructive as well as destructive aspects, depending upon how we can handle them.

Today technology proved to a boon for the lives of millions of peoples specially for who have limited and little access to the tools for the better and sustainable development of the lives of the livelihood. Nanotechnology brings new possibilities, new ideas and new techniques to see the things in a different manner either it is medical sciences to treat some disease using nano-particles or to Information Communication technology through the use of wireless sensors called often originated from micro electromechanical sensors (MEMS) which are smart enough to fit even on the head of a pin specially used in multiplications such as detecting any things from light to surface vibrations, controls building atmosphere, and in various commercialization products.

The molecular structure of nanotechnology is often an inexpensive control of the structure of the matter. We need to study the consequences of the coming revolutions, how it will affect our present situations and what future possibilities we are going to expect from them for the modern societal changes and transformations. The human beings are treated in a more advanced and secure manner as earlier treatment. Technology has developed its branches so vividly and marvelously that its advantages are incredibly countless.

Four Generations

Mihail (Mike) Roco, U.S. National Nanotechnology, has described the four generations of Nanotechnology development as shown in the chart below. The first generated era of integrated nanostructures that functioned like a mammalian cell with hierarchical systems are likely to be developed, the second phase incorporated active nanostructures used for performing multitasks such as sensors, antibiotics, drug devices, actuators etc. Whereas the third nanotechnology phase which came most probably around 2010 featured nanosystems incorporated with

thousands of interacting components. The current nanotechnology system which Roco depicted is of passive nanostructures designed to perform single tasks.

Fig. 1: Sources: Adapted from Centre for responsible Technology (CRN), retrieved from <http://www.crnano.org/whatis.htm>.

NANOTECHNOLOGY APPLICATION

According to U.S. National Science Foundation, nanotechnology is described as “Imagine a medical device that travels through the human body to seek out and destroy small clusters of cancerous cells before they can spread. Or a box no larger than a sugar cube that contains the entire contents of the Library of Congress, or materials much lighter than steel that possesses ten times as much strength.” Nanotechnology has enormous applications in various fields such as electronics, biotechnology, consumer applications, education, nano buildings and nano

infrastructures etc. Today it is being used in creating nano carriers also such as national security, construction, cloth designing, management, packaging, research, patent attorney, fabrication, public service, energy producer, development, sales, teaching, testing, and many more.

Nanotechnology in STEM Education

The nanotechnology is being incorporated in the developed countries but in the countries like India, the incorporation of nanotechnology in various fields is a quite big challenge. The inclusion of nanotechnology in different subjects will promote interdisciplinary approach towards different subjects thereby promoting technological-education in this tectonic era. The nanotechnology with its emerging interdisciplinary approach can best be included in different teaching subjects such as science and technology fields such as sciences, physical sciences, chemistry, biology, electronics, engineering, technology and environmental sciences. In sciences and engineering subject the nanotechnology will be able to develop interactions between and among the sciences that will support teachers and students to develop understanding about the different themes, concepts and phenomenon with respect to various disciplines. Thus through this approach various questions will be coming up in the minds of the teachers and researcher about the advantages of inclusion of nanotechnology in school and higher education. How successfully it can be contributed towards National and International sustainability and development towards science standards and how successfully it can be included in the school curriculum.

According to national Science Standards (NSS), nanotechnology relies concisely on scientific concepts, processes and themes. But one drawback of inclusion of nanotechnology is that at lower education stage some students may not be able to understand properly the concepts of nanostructures and nano particles, although it may lead them to develop solid pillar knowledge about the nanotechnology from the beginning. The important learning should be established for a conceptualized theory framework:

Science: It may be used to provide scientific knowledge about concepts, terms and cause of occurring a particular phenomenon.

Physical Sciences: Nanotechnology can provide broad knowledge spectrum about physical properties of nanostructures and nano-particles, heating and conduction properties, orbital motion, elasticity, wave motion, heat etc.

Biology: Effectively used to teach biology subjects such as cell structures, membrane, cytoplasm, organism structures etc.

Electronics and technology: Address students about the various technological devices and future gadgets, such as smart mobile phones, I-Pods, I-Pads, digital devices, etc. and understanding about the scientific reason behind a particular phenomenon.

Space technology: In understanding about the orbital motion, satellites, atmosphere on moons and mars, and discovery of other life-oriented planets.

Social Perspectives: Supports online social networking thereby changing the modification in the behavior of the society towards technology-based education.

History: Understanding old civilizations and cultures for the modification of present one, nature of scientific knowledge and human evolution theory.

Environmental Sciences: It helps one to understand the concept of environmental components i.e. how to reduce and protect our environment from different organic, biological and social pollutants. It best explains us about the global warming causes and effects and can give best prediction about the weather and future of our environment there improving the quality of our planet.

Medical science: The nanotechnology can effectively and is using in the production of many antibiotics, pills, cancer-medicines, heart diseases, and even nano-particles are developed that can be implanted into the body to fight against cancerous cells or dangerous virus. Its main applications are in medical imaging, anesthesia, transplanting, penicillin, drugs, medicines, X-Rays devices, and surgery.

Future Nano-Robots: The nano robots are the future planning in the field of nanotechnology which is still under pilot-study and hope to come nearby 2025.

CONCLUSIONS:

From the field of biotechnology to information technology, electronic technology to transportation and commercialization, share world to share knowledge, baking sectors to governance, everywhere the technology outshines in one or the other manner. In rural where peoples are hard to find any means of information communication, the weaker sections of the society who remains excluded from the advantages of the education, those who living in far-flung areas experiences problems in communicating with the whole world, or those who could not study due to economical stress and burden- for all of them technology plays an important role in enlighten their path of success.

Calculators at early stage consisted of thousand dollar desktop clunkers, hardly to perform one or two operations, but microelectronics increased their speed using fast processors and made them efficient in size. No one at time could ever think of its size suitable to a child's pocket s and budget. Now in the same magnitude we must have a vision towards everything point of concept often termed as the futuristic approach or vision towards future perspectives. Even, the invention of microscope, nobody could have imagined for such a remarkable progress in the field of electronics and technology. Scientists are continuously working on the recent developments and inventions to shape the future of society in a bright manner. The past technologies such as microwave tubes, robots, satellites, lasers, and superconductors were coming on high rates with narrow applications. The emergence of molecular manufacturing specially in the field of computers through its wide spectrum of applications have made wonders in the field nanotechnology. These growing technologies are continuously replacing and upgrading the factories products.

Nanotechnology thus must be integrated into the present curriculum system especially in the undergraduate degree courses such as sciences, engineering, electronic and technology to promote innovative knowledge of nanotechnology related to all spheres of life. The following zest comes out form the discussions:

- A multi-disciplinary, research-oriented, and practical continuum should be established with the educational institutions and training centers to work together to achieve new heights towards advanced educational system.
- A network of regional hub sites should be developed “Nanotechnology Education Hub Network”
- Nanotechnology must enable portable devices for individualized learning anytime, anywhere and also incorporate upcoming technologies such as brain mapping, brain printing technology etc.
- Centres and hubs for innovative education through nanotechnology must be established where researcher uses nano-enabled devices to s\make something new and innovative.
- Establish horizontal, vertical and system integration in educational curriculum to expand the vision of nano learning and skills. The concepts of nano-engineering, nano structures and nano particles must be introduced at the very early stage of child’s education.
- Use of nanoinformatics and prediction tools in computational science to develop cross-disciplinary module for nanotechnology devices such as tools, devices and gadgets.
- Explore new strategies and techniques for mass production, public related issues, societal changes etc. to promote nanotechnology in a more sophisticated manner.
- Institutions provide fund towards nanotechnologies activities such as top-down and bottom-up research-oriented programs, biotechnology, international programs etc.
- Provision of exploratory and extinctive method towards exposure of multi nano-structured components.
- Supports global collaboration, and coordination with the International organization to maintain the databases, nomenclature, and intellectual properties.
- Advance partnership with NGOs. R & D development sectors, IT, National and International organizations, agencies, educational institutions, research-oriented centre and formation of nanohub.
- Use of simulations and modeling methods in nanotechnology, as it is evolutionary stage and under formative stage.
- New generations should be aware of the physico-chemical-biological research programs using anno structure and anno technology, as an integral part of its applications in the fields.

- Both private and government industries and bodies should foster and collaborate towards incorporation of nanotechnology in terms of partnerships.
- Nanotechnology may use provided an opportunity to be used not in the new emerging areas but also in the traditional industries such as food, paper, wood, fabrics, textiles, and agriculture etc.

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